

Study on Online Shopping Intention for Technology Products among Generation Z in Ho Chi Minh City

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ABSTRACT:

The purpose of this study is to explore the factors influencing the online shopping intentions for technology products among Generation Z in Ho Chi Minh City. The article utilizes an integrated model of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and the extended Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), including the following factors: (1) Perceived Usefulness (CN), (2) Perceived Ease of Use (SD) affecting "Perceived Behavioral Control" (NTKS); (3) Perceived Behavioral Control (NTKS), (4) Subjective Norms (CCQ); (5) Attitude (TD) influencing the "Online shopping intention for technology products among Generation Z in Ho Chi Minh City" (YD). The research results show that "Perceived Behavioral Control" (NTKS) has the strongest impact on the online shopping intentions for technology products among Generation Z (YD), with an influence level of 0.676; the "Subjective Norms" (CCQ) factor has an influence level of 0.295 on the YD variable. The "Perceived Usefulness" (CN) factor has an influence level of 0.628 on NTKS; the "Perceived Ease of Use" (SD) factor has an influence level of 0.295 on NTKS. The "Attitude" (TD) factor does not have statistically significant evidence to conclude its impact on the dependent variable "Online Shopping Intention for Technology Products among Generation Z" (YD). Based on the research findings, the author provides several discussions and suggestions to enhance the online shopping intentions for technology products among Generation Z for manufacturers and businesses in this market.

Keywords: intention, online shopping, technology products, Gen Z, Ho Chi Minh City.

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INTRODUCTION

The development of the Internet and e-commerce has transformed consumer behavior, creating new trends in purchasing and paying for products and services via online platforms. However, the market encompasses a wide range of products, varying in quality, price, and suppliers; consumers are also incredibly diverse. As a result, e-commerce businesses face challenges in understanding the complex behavior of consumers. In Vietnam, particularly in major cities like Ho Chi Minh City, online shopping has become an indispensable part of daily life for many consumers, with Generation Z leading the trend. Generation Z, commonly known as Gen Z, refers to individuals born between 1997 and 2012. They were born and raised in the digital era, with the rapid development of information and communication technology. Not only are they active consumers of technology products, but they are also pioneers in using online services. They are proficient users of digital devices such as smartphones, tablets, laptops, and online platforms like social media, YouTube, TikTok, Netflix, etc..

This strongly influences their intentions and behavior towards online shopping for technology products, leading the research team to pose the crucial question: “What drives Gen Z’s online shopping intention for technology products?”

In the context of the rapid development of information and communication technology, e-commerce has become an integral part of daily life. Technology devices refer to products or tools designed for use in technological activities, particularly in the fields of electronics, telecommunications, computing, and other types of technology. These devices can be hardware, software, or a combination of both. Examples of technology devices include computers, smartphones, digital cameras, tablets, gaming consoles, storage devices, networking equipment, printers, scanners, and many other devices. Technology products are diverse, and since the focus of this study is on the online shopping intentions for technology products among Gen Z, the scope of the research is on individual purchasing behavior, specifically for technology products that serve personal needs. The concept and classification of technology products should focus on high-tech consumer products.

The article applies the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) to explain the online shopping behavior of Gen Z for technology products in Ho Chi Minh City. Ho Chi Minh City is Vietnam’s largest economic center, with a high level of urbanization and a large, young population. This makes it an ideal environment to study the online shopping intentions for technology products, particularly in the context of technology products.

The main objective of the article is to understand the online shopping intentions for technology products among Gen Z in Ho Chi Minh City and the factors influencing these intentions based on the TPB model. The findings will provide specific recommendations for businesses and managers in the technology and e-commerce sectors. Studying the online shopping intentions of Gen Z not only helps researchers gain a better understanding of this group’s consumer behavior but also provides valuable information for businesses in developing marketing and business strategies. Gen Z is predicted to become the main consumer force in the near future; thus, researching their shopping behavior is crucial in shaping consumption trends and promoting sustainable business development.

THEORETICAL BASIS

Concepts

(1) Technology products

In Vietnam, “Technology is a solution, process, or technical know-how that may or may not include tools or means to transform resources into products”. Thus, technology products are goods or services developed and utilized based on advancements and applications in science and technology, designed to meet specific individual needs. These products typically feature advanced functionalities, integrating modern technologies, and providing convenience and high efficiency for users.

These products often introduce innovative solutions to everyday life, work, production, or entertainment challenges. Below are some key characteristics of technology products:

- **Innovation:** Technology products often come with new ideas and inventions, representing progress compared to previous solutions.
- **Application of advanced technology:** They utilize modern techniques, software, hardware, or technologies to function.
- **Utility:** Designed to meet specific user needs, improving efficiency, convenience, or user experience.
- **Connectivity:** Many technology products today can connect to the internet or other devices to exchange information and data.
- **Interactivity:** Technology products often provide a user-friendly interface with high usability and interactivity.

From these characteristics, technology products generally feature advanced functionalities, integrate modern technologies, and offer users significant convenience and efficiency. In the context of new consumer behavior trends among Gen Z, technology products also relate to sustainability, convenience, and social connectivity. In this study, technology products are goods and services developed based on scientific and technological advancements to meet individual usage needs, including:

- Tangible products: Mobile devices (smartphones, tablets), smart wearable devices (smartwatches, fitness bands), smart home appliances (robot vacuums, smart speakers, smart lights), personal entertainment and communication devices (smart TVs, gaming consoles, wireless headphones).
- Intangible products: Software (educational apps, financial management apps, mobile games), mobile applications, cloud storage services (external hard drives, USBs, cloud storage services).

(2) Online shopping intention

Regarding the concept of online shopping, [1] define online shopping as the consumer's behavior of purchasing through online stores or websites using online transactions. [2] state that "online shopping is defined as a service where consumers use internet-connected electronic devices to make shopping transactions". [3] defines online shopping as purchasing through electronic connections between buyers and sellers—typically online.

It is evident that the common point among these concepts is that online shopping refers to the behavior of purchasing goods or services via the internet. Specifically, online shopping involves finding a product of interest by accessing e-commerce platforms/ websites/ retailer apps/ social networks using a shopping search tool. The interface of these online shopping channels allows displaying detailed information about products and prices. When customers place an order, the goods are delivered to them without needing to visit the store or engage in direct communication between buyer and seller.

Intention is a factor used to assess the likelihood of future behavior; it can be measured by the consumer's expectation to shop and their consideration of the product/service in the future. According to [4], when a customer intends to use online transactions for shopping, it is called online shopping intention. [5] defines intention as "indicators of how hard people are willing to try, how much effort they plan to exert." Behavioral intention is central to the TPB theory and is the main predictor of purchasing behavior [5]. Purchase intention is the motivation that drives consumers to buy a product or service in a specific shopping environment [6]. Similarly, according to [7], purchase intention is a decision-making process that shows the motivation behind why customers buy a specific product. [8] claims that purchase intention is a key predictor of consumer buying behavior. Thus, online shopping intention refers to a customer's willingness to purchase goods through the internet. The online shopping intention for technology products among Gen Z means the intention of Gen Z customers to purchase technology products from online channels, including e-commerce platforms and social networks.

(3) Generation Z

According to research by [9], Generation Z, also known as "digital natives," has grown up in a digital environment and tends to prioritize the use of technology in their daily activities. They easily access and use the latest technology products and frequently update themselves with technological advancements. This trend drives the online shopping intention for technology products among Gen Z.

During the shopping process, Gen Z relies on online reviews and advice from social media influencers to make purchasing decisions, especially for technology products [10]. Research by [11] indicates that Gen Z values convenience and personalized experiences when shopping online. They prefer shopping platforms that offer a good user experience, easy product searches, and quality customer service. This is especially important for technology products, where detailed information and product reviews play a crucial role in purchasing decisions. Gen Z is not only an active consumer of technology products but also shapes future consumer trends. Understanding the needs and

consumer behavior of Gen Z is key to success for technology companies and retailers in an increasingly competitive business environment.

According to a report by [12], Gen Z tends to engage in omnichannel shopping, combining both online and offline. They use online channels to research products, compare prices, and look for deals but are also willing to visit physical stores to experience the product before purchasing. Although the research focuses on online shopping intentions, this trend should also be studied by businesses to create an omnichannel sales system that better serves the needs of Gen Z.

Research Overview

In the context of the growing popularity of online shopping, understanding the factors influencing consumer shopping intentions, especially among Generation Z, is crucial. Two prominent theories in this research are the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB).

(1) Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed by [13], is one of the most popular models to explain users' motivations and behaviors toward technology. According to TAM, two main factors influence technology acceptance: perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU).

- Perceived Usefulness (PU): This is the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system will enhance their job performance.
- Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU): This is the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system will be free of effort.

Online shopping offers many advantages such as discounts, time savings, and the elimination of certain physical difficulties associated with traditional shopping [14]. With e-commerce platforms, customers can browse the platform, compare features and prices of products from different sellers (manufacturers, retailers), and choose the products they want [15]. The diversity of products sold on e-commerce platforms is rapidly increasing, with many suppliers joining these platforms. This increases customers' ability to find suitable products and attracts more customers to use e-commerce platforms, thereby driving the growth of the e-commerce market in the future [16].

(2) Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), developed by [5], focuses on three main factors influencing intentions and behavior:

- Attitude: The individual's evaluation of online shopping for technology products.
- Perceived Behavioral Control: The individual's perception of their ability to control and perform the online shopping behavior.
- Subjective Norms: The social pressures and opinions regarding online shopping behavior.

[5] defines attitude towards a behavior as "the degree to which a person has a favorable or unfavorable evaluation or appraisal of the behavior in question." Both TPB and TAM identify attitude as an important predictor of behavioral intention [17,18]. The study on online shopping intentions for technology products by [19] identified attitude along with other factors, including perceived behavioral control, as having significant effects on online shopping intentions.

Proposed Model, Hypotheses, and Research Scales

This study focuses on the online shopping intentions for technology products of Gen Z consumers in Ho Chi Minh City by using an integrated model of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and the extended Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). The specific research model is as follows:

Figure 1. Proposed Research Model
Source: Research Team Proposal

Research Hypotheses: The research model illustrated in the figure above is explained with the following research hypotheses:

- Hypothesis H1: Attitude towards online shopping (TD) has a positive correlation with the intention to shop online for technology products (YD).
- Hypothesis H2: Subjective Norms (CCQ) have a positive correlation with the intention to shop online for technology products (YD).
- Hypothesis H3: Perceived Behavioral Control (NTKS) has a positive correlation with the intention to shop online for technology products (YD).
- Hypothesis H4: Perceived Usefulness (CN) has a positive correlation with Perceived Behavioral Control (NTKS).
- Hypothesis H5: Perceived Ease of Use (SD) has a positive correlation with Perceived Behavioral Control (NTKS).

The research scale components are presented in the following table:

Table 1. Explanation of Factors and Measurement Scales

Variable name	Measurement Scale	Source
1. Perceived Usefulness (CN): This is the degree to which an individual believes that online shopping for technological products will bring benefits and help achieve personal goals. When users perceive usefulness, they are more likely to make purchases.		
CN1	Online shopping helps me save time.	[20,21]
CN2	Using online shopping services helps me save costs (with many promotions and discounts).	
CN3	Online shopping makes it easy for me to purchase authentic technology products.	
CN4	Online shopping allows me to easily receive advice and answers from sellers.	
2. Perceived Ease of Use (SD): This is the degree to which an individual believes that using a specific technology will require minimal effort. If users find online shopping easy to use, it will lead to purchasing behavior.		
SD1	I find it easy to search for necessary information about technology products on online shopping channels.	[13]
SD2	I find online shopping platforms to have user-friendly and easy-to-use interfaces.	
SD3	I find paying online for technology products is easy.	

3. Attitude (TD): An individual's evaluation of online shopping for technological products.		
TD1	I find online shopping for technology products to be enjoyable.	[5]
TD2	I find online shopping to be safer than traditional shopping.	
TD3	Online shopping is easier than traditional shopping because it has reviews and comments from other users.	
4. Perceived Behavioral Control (NTKS): An individual's evaluation of their ability to control and carry out online shopping behavior.		
NTKS1	I have sufficient time resources for online shopping for technological products.	[5]
NTKS2	I have sufficient financial resources for online shopping for technological products.	
NTKS3	I have the necessary knowledge and ability to shop online for technological products.	
5. Subjective Norms (CCQ): Opinions and social pressure regarding online shopping behavior.		
CCQ1	My family supports me in online shopping for technological products.	[5,21]
CCQ2	My friends support my online shopping for technological products.	
CCQ3	News and advertisements influence my online shopping for technological products.	
CCQ4	Social media has a normal influence on my intention to shop online for technological products.	
6. Purchase Intention (YD): Consumers' intention to shop online for technological products.		
YD1	I intend to shop online for technological products in the near future.	[4,5]
YD2	I am certain to shop online for technological products when the need arises.	
YD3	I am willing to recommend online shopping for technological products to friends and family.	

Source: Proposed by the research group

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study uses a survey method to collect data from Generation Z respondents in Ho Chi Minh City. The survey questions are designed based on the influencing factors in the proposed model and the corresponding measurement scales. The study integrates the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) with some extensions and modifications from previous research. The research proposes a model with six hypotheses derived from the literature review. In this study, the questionnaire is designed in two parts:

- Questions to gather general information about the respondents.
- Questions to collect respondents' perceptions regarding each measurement scale corresponding to the six factors in the proposed research model.

The content of the questionnaire was discussed with experts in the field, and a pilot study with 10 respondents was used to refine the questionnaire. The online questionnaire (Google Form: <https://forms.gle/7LW7QKtVMBfNvRnaA>) was distributed to potential respondents, targeting Generation Z consumers in Ho Chi Minh City. The research group received 228 responses, with 200 respondents having previously purchased technological products online and continuing to answer questions about influencing factors, while 28 respondents who had not purchased online answered questions about reasons for not doing so. Each item in this study was measured using a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 ("strongly disagree") to 5 ("strongly agree"). The PLS method was employed for analysis.

Data Analysis

The collected data will be analyzed using PLS software to assess the relationship between input factors and the online purchase intention of technological products among Generation Z consumers. The general structural regression equation is as follows:

$$INT = a*TD + b*CCQ + c*NTKS$$

$$NTKS = e*CN + f*SD$$

The SMARTPLS software was used to test hypotheses and evaluate the impact of the factors.

Step 1: Evaluation of the Measurement Model

The measurement model was assessed by examining values for scale reliability, the quality of observed variables, convergent validity, and discriminant validity.

Step 2: Evaluation of the Structural Model

Once the measurement model met the requirements, the structural model was evaluated by analyzing impact relationships, path coefficients, the overall determination coefficient (R-squared), and the effect size (f-squared).

From the collected primary and secondary data, the research group processed, tabulated, and created charts to compare and analyze, answering the research questions and clarifying the objectives set in the study.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Descriptive statistics of the sample

The survey collected 228 responses. Among the respondents, 103 were male (45.1%), 120 were female (52.5%), and 5 did not specify their gender (2.4%). In terms of age, 77.5% were aged between 12 and under 18 years old, 12.5% were between 18 and under 23 years old, and 10% were between 23 and 26 years old. Most of the participants were students (75%) with an income of under 5 million VND (80%).

Online shopping is no longer unfamiliar to the youth. Out of the 228 respondents, 200 were aware of online shopping (87.7%), while 28 were not (12.3%). Therefore, in the analysis of factors affecting the online shopping intention of Generation Z in Ho Chi Minh City, only the responses of 200 individuals were considered.

Figure 2. Online Shopping Platforms for Technology Products Used by Survey Participants

Source: Survey data from the research team

With a checkbox question regarding the online shopping channels of Generation Z in Ho Chi Minh City, the results show that Generation Z mainly chooses e-commerce platforms such as Shopee, Lazada, Tiki, TikTok shop... (93.5%); social networks (32.3%); the official websites of tech product manufacturers (29%); and other channels (through friends or acquaintances) accounting for 19.4%.

Among the 28 respondents who were unaware of online shopping (12.3%), the reasons for not purchasing are illustrated in the chart:

Figure 3. Reasons why Generation Z does not Purchase Technology Products Online

Source: Survey data from the research team

The most common reasons for not purchasing technology products online are concerns about poor product quality (58.8%), difficulties with product warranty (35.3%), and a lack of product variety (29.4%)

Results of the Evaluation of the Quality of Observable Variables in the Measurement Model

Results of the evaluation of the quality of observable variables in the measurement model evaluation of the quality of observable variables

After running the model for the first time, the quality of the observable variables was evaluated using the outer loadings coefficient. The quality of the observable variables affecting the intention to purchase technology products online is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Outer Loadings of Factors Affecting the Intention to Purchase Technology Products Online among Generation Z

	CCQ	CN	NTKS	SD	TD	YD
CCQ1	0,814					
CCQ2	0,905					
CCQ3	0,906					
CCQ4	0,745					
CN1		0,905				
CN2		0,875				
CN3		0,840				
CN4		0,905				
NTKS1			0,915			
NTKS2			0,917			
NTKS3			0,916			
SD1				0,937		
SD2				0,941		
SD3				0,924		
TD2					0,883	
TD3					0,879	
YD1						0,939
YD2						0,939
YD3						0,920
TD1					0,865	

Source: Research team's test results

The results from Table 2 show that the outer loadings of all the total correlation coefficients of the variables influencing Generation Z's intention to shop online for technology products (all > 0.7) [22] indicate that the observed variables are significant.

Scale reliability testing

The reliability of the scale for the factors affecting Generation Z's intention to shop online for technology products was assessed using SMARTPLS through two main indices: Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR).

Table 3. Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability of Factors Affecting Generation Z's Intention to Shop Online for Technology Products

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
CCQ	0,866	0,891	0,908	0,714
CN	0,904	0,907	0,933	0,778
NTKS	0,904	0,905	0,940	0,839
SD	0,927	0,928	0,953	0,872
TD	0,848	0,849	0,908	0,767
YD	0,926	0,926	0,953	0,870

Source: Research group's test results

According to Table 3, after reliability testing using Cronbach's Alpha, the results for the factors are as follows: Subjective Norms (CCQ) reached 0.866; Perceived Usefulness (CN) reached 0.904; Perceived Behavioral Control (NTKS) reached 0.904; Perceived Ease of Use (SD) reached 0.927; Attitude towards Online Shopping (TD) reached 0.8458; Intention to Purchase Technology Products Online of Generation Z (YD) reached 0.926. Therefore, all the scales satisfy the condition of > 0.7 [23] and do not violate any rule that requires variable elimination, so no variables were excluded, and the reliability is acceptable.

The Composite Reliability (CR) of all observed variables is also > 0.7 [24] (Table 3). Thus, the scale is reliable, meaningful for analysis, and can be used for the next factor analysis.

Convergence Validity

According to the data analysis results in Table 3, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each factor is as follows: Subjective Norms (CCQ) reached 0.714; Intention to Purchase Technology Products Online of Generation Z (YD) reached 0.870; Perceived Usefulness (CN) reached 0.778; Perceived Behavioral Control (NTKS) reached 0.839; Perceived Ease of Use (SD) reached 0.872; Attitude towards Online Shopping (TD) reached 0.767. Thus, the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) for all variables is > 0.5 [25], indicating that the model satisfies the conditions for convergence.

Discriminant Validity

The results in Table 4 show the Fornell-Larcker criteria for the research model's factors, including Subjective Norms (CCQ); Intention to purchase Technology Products Online of Generation Z (YD); Perceived Usefulness of Online Shopping (CN); Perceived Behavioral Control of Online Shopping (NTKS); Perceived Ease of Use (SD); and Attitude towards Online Shopping (TD). All meet the criteria for discriminant validity because the square root of the AVE values on the diagonal are higher than the values outside the diagonal. Therefore, in terms of discriminant validity, both the cross-loadings and the Fornell-Larcker criteria meet the conditions.

Table 4. Fornell-Larcker Criteria for the Research Model of Factors Affecting Generation Z's Intention to Shop Online for Technology Products

	CCQ	CN	NTKS	SD	TD	YD
CCQ	0,845					
CN	0,810	0,882				
NTKS	0,759	0,876	0,916			
SD	0,687	0,841	0,823	0,934		

TD	0,613	0,581	0,565	0,441	0,876	
YD	0,775	0,844	0,869	0,828	0,509	0,933

Source: Survey data from the research team

The value of the function f^2

The value of the function f^2 represents the degree of impact of the structure (factor) when removed from the model. The f^2 values corresponding to 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 represent small, medium, and large effect sizes [26] of exogenous variables, respectively. If the effect size < 0.02 , it is considered to have no impact.

Table 5. Summary of Values f^2

	CCQ	CN	NTKS	SD	TD	YD
CCQ						0,154
CN			0,560			
NTKS						0,879
SD			0,123			
TD						0,008
YD						

Source: Survey data from the research team

In this model, in Table 5, we see the f^2 values for the factors: Perceived Usefulness of Online Shopping (CN) reaches $0.560 > 0.35$ (indicating a large effect); Perceived Ease of Use (SD) reaches 0.123 (with $0.02 < f^2 < 0.15$, indicating a small effect); Perceived Behavioral Control of Online Shopping (NTKS) reaches $0.879 > 0.35$ (indicating a large effect); the factor: Subjective Norms (CCQ) reaches 0.154 (with $0.15 < f^2 < 0.35$, indicating a medium effect); Attitude towards Online Shopping (TD) (0.008) has $f^2 < 0.02$, meaning it is considered to have no influence on YD.

Results of Influence Assessment Using Structural Model

Evaluating the Relationships and Their Influence

The relationships and the level of influence of the factors affecting the intention to purchase technology products online among Generation Z on SMARTPLS are illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Factors Affecting the Intention to Purchase Technology Products Online among Generation z

Source: Results of Testing by the Research Group Using SMARTPLS

The results of the Bootstrap analysis to assess the relationships and their influence are shown in Table 6. Accordingly, the variables:

Table 6. Path Coefficient of the Structural Model

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
CCQ -> YD	0,295	0,297	0,072	4,091	0,000
CN -> NTKS	0,628	0,633	0,081	7,769	0,000
NTKS -> YD	0,676	0,673	0,055	12,238	0,000
SD -> NTKS	0,295	0,289	0,094	3,121	0,002
TD -> YD	-0,054	-0,052	0,043	1,244	0,214

Source: Results of testing by the Research Group Using SMARTPLS

Perceived Usefulness of Online Shopping (CN) and Perceived Ease of Use (SD) have an influence on the factor Perceived Behavioral Control (NTKS), with P-values < 0.05.

Subjective Norms (CCQ) and Perceived Behavioral Control of Online Shopping (NTKS) have an influence on the "Intention to Purchase Technology Products Online among Generation Z (YD)," with P-values < 0.05 (hypotheses H2, H3, H4, and H5 are accepted). However, Attitude towards Online Shopping (TD) has P-values > 0.05, indicating that this factor is not statistically significant in demonstrating a positive relationship with the intention to purchase technology products online among Generation Z (hypothesis H1 is not accepted).

The test results in Table 6 show that with a 95% confidence level, "Perceived Behavioral Control" (NTKS) has the strongest influence on the intention to purchase technology products online among Generation Z (YD), with an impact level of 0.676. The factor "Subjective Norms" (CCQ) has an influence level of 0.295 on the YD variable.

The factor "Perceived Usefulness" (CN) has an influence level of 0.628 on NTKS, while the factor "Perceived Ease of Use" (SD) has an influence level of 0.295 on NTKS;

The factor "Attitude" does not have sufficient statistical significance to conclude its influence on the dependent variable "Intention to Purchase Technology Products Online among Generation Z" (YD).

Therefore, we have the following regression equation:

$$YD = 0.295*CCQ+0.676*NTKS \quad (1)$$

$$NTKS=0.628*CN+0.295*SD \quad (2)$$

Evaluation of the Overall Coefficient of Determination R² (R square)

The results of the PLS Algorithm analysis provide the R² value, reflecting the extent to which the independent variables explain the dependent variable. The R² value measures the overall coefficient of determination (R-square value), which is an indicator for measuring the model's fit with the data (the model's explanatory power). According to [22], the suggested R-square values are 0.75, 0.50, or 0.25.

Table 7. The Coefficient of Determination (R²) of Independent Variables for the Dependent Variable

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
NTKS	0,794	0,791
YD	0,788	0,785

Source: Results of Testing by the Research Group

The results from Table 7 show that the variable (YD) has an R² of 0.788 and an adjusted R² of 0.785, while the variable (NTKS) has an R² of 0.794 and an adjusted R² of 0.791. Thus, the independent variables CCQ and NTKS in the model explain 78.8% of the variation in the YD variable, and the variables CN and SD explain 79.4% of the variation in the NTKS variable.

Evaluation of the Reliability Index (SRMR)

The Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) index indicates the goodness of fit of the research model. According to [27], a well-fitting model typically has an SRMR value of less than 0.08.

Table 8. Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) Reliability Index

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.056	0.061

Source: Results of Testing by the Research Group

According to the SRMR results in Table 8, the SRMR value of the research model is 0.056, which is less than 0.08. Therefore, this model is suitable for data analysis.

DISCUSSION

Factors Affecting the Mediating Variable “Perceived Behavioral Control” (NTKS)

The research results, based on the average values of the factors affecting the intention to purchase technology products online among Generation Z, show that two factors—perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use—affect the mediating variable “perceived behavioral control” (NTKS), as reflected in the regression equation: **NTKS= 0.628*CN+0.295*SD**

- The factor “Perceived Usefulness” (CN) of online shopping consistently achieves a relatively high average score, ranging from 3.805 to 3.925 on a 5-point scale. Specifically (Figure 5):
- The factor **CN2**, “Using online shopping services helps save costs,” received the highest average score (3.925). Consumers highly value the discounts and promotions available when shopping online, making this an important factor driving them to choose this shopping method.
- The factor **CN4**, “Online shopping makes it easy for me to consult and get answers from sellers,” received a score of 3.895. This reflects the consumer’s interest in the quality of consulting and support services provided by sellers during the shopping process.

Figure 5. Survey Results for the Factor “Perceived Usefulness” (CN)

Source: Survey Results by the Research Group

- The factor **CN1**, “Online shopping helps me save time,” received an average score of 3.805, the lowest among the factors but still relatively high. The results show that consumers clearly perceive the time-saving benefits of online shopping compared to traditional shopping.
- Finally, the factor **CN3**, “Online shopping makes it easier for me to buy authentic technology products,” scored 3.81, indicating that consumers still have a certain level of trust in purchasing authentic technology products through online channels.

Perceived Ease of Use (SD)

The survey results on the factor “Perceived ease of use” reflect a positive perception among consumers regarding the convenience of online shopping channels, especially in terms of information search, ease of payment, and user experience. The average scores for the variables were as follows: “I find it easy to search for information on technology products on online shopping platforms” at 3.96, “I find online shopping platforms have a user-friendly and easy-to-use interface” at 3.9, and “I find it easy to make online payments for technology products” at 3.915.

Figure 6. Survey Results for the Factor “Perceived Ease of Use” (SD)

Source: Survey Results by the Research Group

These factors all play an important role in encouraging Gen Z consumers to choose online shopping for technology products, including enhancing their ability to search for product information, improving the user-friendliness of the interface, and making online payments easier.

Factors Affecting the Intention to Purchase Technology Products Online among Gen Z

The influence of perceived behavioral control and subjective norms on the intention to purchase technology products online among Gen Z is reflected in the following regression equation:

$$YD = 0.295*CCQ+0.676*NTKS \quad (3)$$

- The factor “Perceived Behavioral Control” has a greater influence on the intention to purchase technology products online (0.676) compared to the subjective norms factor (0.295). Variables related to perceived behavioral control, such as the ability to manage time, financial resources, and necessary knowledge, all achieved relatively high average scores of 3.765, 3.855, and 3.86, respectively. These results indicate that Gen Z tends to feel confident in their ability to control the necessary resources when shopping online, especially in terms of finances and knowledge. This also means that issues related to skills or finances are not barriers for this group when it comes to online shopping.

Figure 7. Survey Results for the Factor “Perceived Behavioral Control” (NTKS)
Source: Survey results

- The factor of subjective norms, related to support from family, friends, as well as the influence of media and social networks, has a lower average score, ranging from 3.35 to 3.745. Notably, the social network variable has the lowest influence (3.35), indicating that while social media is a popular information channel, its influence on Gen Z’s purchasing decisions is not as significant as other factors. However, support from family and friends still plays a more important role, highlighting the significance of social relationships in the purchasing decisions of Gen Z in Ho Chi Minh City.

Figure 8. Survey Results for the Factor “Subjective Norms” (CCQ)
Source: Survey results

The survey results on the online shopping intentions for technology products among Gen Z in Ho Chi Minh City reveal the average scores for three variables in ascending order as follows: “Intention to shop online for technology products in the near future” scored 3.915; “Certainly will shop online for technology products when needed” scored 3.87; and the highest score was for “Willing to recommend online shopping for technology products to friends and family”, which scored 3.935.

These results indicate that Gen Z in Ho Chi Minh City not only tends to shop online for technology products in the near future but is also willing to recommend this experience to their friends and family. This reflects a high level of trust and satisfaction with current online shopping services and a tendency to spread and share positive experiences with others. The willingness to recommend

products is a positive sign that service providers have successfully built trust and loyalty among customers and highlights the importance of maintaining and enhancing service quality to attract and retain users, as well as to generate positive word-of-mouth within the community.

However, the score for “certainly will shop online when needed” is lower, suggesting that there may still be factors that need improvement to ensure that consumers actually choose to shop online when they have a need, such as optimizing user experience, providing better support services, or enhancing relevant promotional programs.

Figure 9. Survey Results for “Intention to Shop Online for Technology Products among Gen Z in Ho Chi Minh city”
 Source: Survey results

It can be seen that online shopping channels have created a positive impression regarding convenience. However, to achieve greater perfection in the eyes of consumers, further improvements are needed. The authors propose several solutions to suggest to online shopping service providers for better improvement and service:

Enhance the Usefulness and Diversity of Online Shopping Platforms

- **Diversify promotions and offers:** The research results show that cost savings are a significant factor affecting perceived usefulness. Therefore, providers should focus on offering more attractive and personalized promotions and deals that cater to the needs and shopping habits of Gen Z.
- **Improve convenience and efficiency during the shopping process:** Enhance product interaction on the shopping platform, such as providing detailed information, high-quality images and videos, and product comparison features. This helps users make purchasing decisions based on visual and specific information.

(ii) Improve user experience

- **Design a user-friendly and easy-to-use interface:** Results indicate that a user-friendly and easy-to-use interface is crucial for Gen Z. Therefore, continue optimizing the user interface, organizing products by specific categories/themes to enhance customer search capabilities; ensure that steps from searching for products, making payments, to receiving items are simple and easy to handle. Additionally, ensure compatibility across various devices such as mobile phones, tablets, and desktops.
- **Enhance the ordering and payment process:** To increase the perception of ease of use, the payment process needs to be designed to be simple, fast, and secure. Integrating various payment methods (e-wallets, credit cards, transfers) and optimizing the payment experience can help improve user satisfaction.
- **Increase the provision of information and usage guides:** To improve perceived behavioral control, providers should offer more guidance materials, videos, and detailed articles on how to use the platform, choose suitable products, and effective shopping tips. This helps users feel more confident when shopping online.

- **Provide quick and effective customer support:** Customer support teams need to be well-trained to answer users' questions quickly and accurately. 24/7 support through various channels such as live chat, email, and phone will help users feel more secure when shopping. After-sales service should be emphasized to provide consumers with peace of mind and fulfill all product/service commitments. For technology products, warranty, return, compensation, and complaint policies should be detailed and publicly disclosed alongside product information.

Enhance the Impact of Subjective Norms

- **Leverage social media effectively:** Although social media currently does not have a significant impact on purchasing decisions, investing in social media strategies can improve this. Marketing campaigns through influencers or social media promotions can increase awareness and support from family and friends regarding Gen Z's online shopping.
- **Build online communities:** Creating user communities that share experiences, product reviews, or discuss new technology trends is also a way to increase the influence of the social environment on users' purchasing decisions.

CONCLUSION

The research results indicate the level of influence of factors affecting the intention to shop online for technology products among Gen Z in Ho Chi Minh City. The study shows that the intention to shop online for technology products among Gen Z in Ho Chi Minh City is influenced by subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, perceived usefulness, and perceived ease of use impacting perceived behavioral control. This indicates that while shopping online, Gen Z tends to be self-reliant regarding the resources and knowledge needed, while still being significantly influenced by social factors (subjective norms). The results reflect a positive view of consumers regarding the usefulness of online shopping channels, particularly in information search, ease of payment, and user experience. This opens new research directions on better leveraging social media channels and social relationships to boost online shopping intentions among the younger generation. Along with the convenience and randomness of the survey, there are limitations regarding sample size and questionnaire quality. Additionally, the model only explains 79.4% of the "intention to shop online for technology products among Gen Z in Ho Chi Minh City." The results are considered a guideline for further research on the online shopping intentions of Gen Z. In the future, the research team could expand the survey to a broader scope, add more factors, and selectively filter respondents to increase sample size and questionnaire quality, as well as the explanatory power of the model.

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